

CHARACTERISATION OF BINDER POWDERS IN GLASS FIBRE FABRICS USING LASER MICROSCOPY AND DEEP LEARNING SEGMENTATION METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Binder-stabilised preforms offer significant advantages in structural composite manufacturing, enhancing handling, repeatability, and overall process efficiency. However, the heterogeneous structure of the fabric, influenced by fibre orientations, binder powder distribution, and stitching patterns, presents challenges for process control and performance prediction. A detailed characterisation of these microstructural features is essential for optimising manufacturing parameters and ensuring consistent material properties. Laser microscopy combined with image analysis provides a powerful tool for quantifying these structural variations. Classical segmentation techniques, however, struggle to accurately delineate key features due to low contrast and complex material interfaces. In this work, we employ a deep learning-based segmentation approach using a U-Net model to overcome these challenges. The model enables robust segmentation of microscopy images, allowing for the extraction of critical microstructural properties, such as binder coverage, particle size distribution, and anisotropy, providing a quantitative basis for further analysis. The findings highlight the potential of deep learning in advancing automated image analysis for composite materials, paving the way for more data-driven approaches in material characterisation and process optimisation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Binder-powdered glass fibre fabrics show potential in composite manufacturing to create stable preforms that enable efficient, large-scale production e.g. for the wind turbine industry. Applying a polymer binder powder to the glass fibre fabrics gives the consolidated preforms mechanical stability upon activation (i.e. heat treatment under glass transition temperature), allowing them to be manipulated and transported. This stabilisation is essential for vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) and similar processes, where consistent fibre distribution within preforms helps improve the flow of resin and, consequently, the overall quality of the final composite material.[1–5] Moreover, the use of binder powdered fabrics has the potential to parallelise the production stage, where the glass fibre fabrics are placed in the mould, ultimately reducing the lead time and cost associated with large-scale composite manufacturing.[6–8]

Despite the potential for widespread industrial application of binder powdered glass fibre fabrics (BP-GFF), current knowledge on the microstructural influence of binder powders is limited, particularly concerning how they interact with the fibres. The complex morphology of the binder powders and their heterogeneous distribution within the fibre preform poses multiple challenges for modelling the process. Existing methods often rely on simplified assumptions that do not capture the intricacies of the binder distribution and do not accurately represent the fibre-matrix interface.[9] This gap in robust modelling methodologies limits the predictability and optimisation of the manufacturing process, making it difficult to standardise quality control measures. As a result, there is a pressing need for more advanced characterisation techniques to facilitate accurate preform structure modelling and enhance binder powder composites' reliability.

Laser scanning confocal microscopy offers a promising approach by providing high-resolution imaging of BP-GFFs, enabling detailed analysis of the binder's distribution and morphology.[10]

These high-resolution images can be segmented through advanced image processing techniques to characterise the binder topology. Traditional segmentation methods, such as intensity threshold and feature-based segmentation, perform poorly for segmenting the laser microscopy images as the segmentation classes do not have separation in the intensity values nor the basic features. More recent advancements in machine learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), allow for improved accuracy in segmenting complex, irregular structures. Badran et al. (2020) employed a deep neural network to segment 3D tomography images of SiC–SiC composites (i.e where fibre and matrix were made of same material), thereby facilitating automated analysis of fibre distribution and matrix cracking.[11] Hong et al. (2021) developed a deep learning model to segment short fibres in glass fibre reinforced concrete using X-ray micro-computed tomography images.[12] Guo et al. (2023) demonstrated the use of a U-Net for precise fibre segmentation in time-resolved computed tomography (CT) scans.[13] Vorobev et al. (2023) applied deep learning models to segment structural defects in polymer composite CT images, improving the detection of defects.[14] Dong et al. (2024) applied a U-Net model for segmenting 2D optical images to characterise the microstructure of fibre-hybrid polymer composites.[15]

In this study, we train and deploy a deep CNN based on U-Net to improve the segmentation of binders and glass fibres in laser scanning microscopy images of BF-GFFs.

2 DATA

The considered fabrics are Unidirectional Non-Crimp glass fibre Fabrics (UD NCF) and Biaxial (Biax) glass fibre fabrics, to which a semi-transparent polymer binder powder has been applied on the top surface of the fabrics. Both fabrics were acquired with the binder powder already applied.

The laser microscopy images are obtained using an Olympus LEXT laser microscope[16] using a 10X zoom objective and stitching multiple scans to cover more surface area than a single scan can. An example of a 4x4 stitched microscopy image of a UD NCF BP-GFF is shown below in fig. 1.

Figure 1: Laser scanning microscopy image of a UD NCF glass fibre fabric with polymer binder powder applied.

3 METHODS

3.1 Classical image segmentation methods

As seen on the microscopy image, the segmentation of binder powder and glass fibres is not a trivial task. The inherent features making the task difficult are, among others: 1) No significant contrast between binder powder and glass fibres. 2) Binder powders are semi-transparent, and the glass fibre structures come through. 3) The low contrast stitching makes the binder powder difficult to detect. Furthermore, manual segmentation is not a viable solution either, as even for quite small surface areas as the one shown in Fig. 1, there will be hundreds of particles present, making manual annotation of every one of them impractical.

These image features make it a difficult task to obtain good segmentations through classical imaging techniques. Intensity threshold and watershed methods will yield poor results, as there is no clear separation between classes in the intensity spectrum. More advanced methods, like the implementation [17] of the Structure Tensor method, which has previously been used to characterise fibre directions [18], can usually segment fibre images due to the directional information in the images. However, as the binder powder is semi-transparent, the directional information of the underlying glass fibres is also found in areas containing binder particles. Furthermore, the areas with stitching are also without any directional information and will therefore falsely be classified as binders. Therefore, these methods are inadequate for the segmentation task at hand.

3.2 Deep Learning segmentation

The dataset for training the deep learning segmentation model is established by cropping the original dataset into 512x512-pixel patches. Given the 8 original high-resolution images, this yields a total of 278 image patches. Of those, 90% (250 patches) will be used for training, and 10% (28 patches) will be used as the validation set during training. To guide the training, the images are partially annotated, separating areas that are binder powder and areas that are not binder powder. These masks have been encoded into three classes: $\{0, 1, 2\} = \{\text{Unknown}, \text{Not Binder Powder}, \text{Binder powder}\}$. Similarly to the original images, the masks are cropped into 278 patches, such that each training image patch has a corresponding mask patch holding some ground truth information.

The architecture used for the deep learning segmentation task is a U-Net, originally proposed by Ronneberger et al. (2015) [19]. In comparison with other architectures, U-Nets have proved excellent performance in image segmentation as the visual information is restored through the encoder-decoder architecture. U-Nets do, in general, perform well on smaller datasets. The chosen architecture is further of the type utilising the deep CNN ResNet34 [20] as the backbone, where the ResNet34 is pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset [21]. The loss function used in the training of the U-Net is weighted categorical cross-entropy loss [22], where the classes $\{0, 1, 2\}$ are assigned weight $\{0.0, 1.0, 1.0\}$, meaning no weight on the areas having no label and equal weight on the labelled areas. The network is trained using an ADAM optimiser for 200 epochs, showing a convergence of the training and validation losses in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Training and validation loss curves for the U-Net segmentation model over 200 epochs.

4 RESULTS

The segmentation for a microscopy image produced by the U-Net segmentation model is shown in Fig. 3. The model has not seen this microscopy image during training, and therefore, it can be used to validate the model's performance.

Figure 3: Microscopy image of a UD NCF BP-GFF (left) and corresponding U-Net segmentation output (right). Red pixels indicate binder powder; blue pixels indicate non-binder regions. This image was not part of the training set and is used for model validation.

Conferring Fig. 3, it can be difficult to assess whether the segmentation is a proper pixel-wise division of the microscopy image into the classes: binder powder and not binder powder. But certain metrics can aid in the assessment of the quality of the segmentation. The Intersection-over-Union (IoU) and Dice scores, both commonly used in the realm of image segmentation, are used in this study.

$$IoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}, \quad Dice = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|} \quad (1)$$

where A and B are the segmentation and annotation, respectively.

To properly compare the performance of each of the segmentation methods, IoU and Dice scores are computed for each of the methods against the annotation mask. The scores are only computed with regard to the annotated area corresponding to known classes. Furthermore, the confusion matrix is computed to evaluate the classification. The image used for validation is an image of UD NCF glass fibre fabrics that was acquired on the Olympus LEXT [16] from another sample, on another day, and that has not been part of either the training or the validation dataset. The image is the one shown in Fig. 3. This is to verify the robustness of the method, as it has to work on data that has not been seen by the model, while acquired under similar conditions to the training data.

Figure 4: (Left) Intersection-over-Union (IoU) and Dice scores comparing classical and deep learning segmentation methods. (Right) Normalised confusion matrix for the U-Net model, showing 96% classification accuracy and balanced performance across classes.

As discussed, the scores in Fig. 4 demonstrate the fundamental limitations of classical methods in segmenting the microscopy images. The watershed approach fails to produce a meaningful segmentation, while intensity thresholding performs slightly better but remains insufficient for obtaining reliable segmentation results. This outcome is expected, as the image intensity spectrum lacks clear class separation. The structure tensor method using a fractional anisotropy measure

achieves a further improvement over the previous methods. However, its segmentation quality remains inadequate for meaningful post-processing. The U-Net segmentation model improves the scores significantly, as is seen in Fig. 4 (Left), where both IoU and Dice scores indicate a near-perfect match to the annotations. To further quantify the performance of the U-Net segmentation model, the normalised confusion matrix, Fig. 4 (Right), provides insights into how the classification performs and where it classifies incorrectly. Here it can be seen that the model correctly predicts 96% of the pixels in each class, with a very low and equal rate of misclassification. This shows that there is no clear bias in the segmentation model. In total, this indicates that the segmentation model is successful and that the segmentation can be used for further processing.

The U-Net segmentation results provide a foundation for further analysis of material properties in the microscopy images. By leveraging the U-Net segmentation model, key characteristics such as binder coverage, particle size distribution, and particle aspect ratios can be quantified. These derived properties offer valuable insights into the material's composition and morphology, enabling a more detailed assessment. The U-Net segmentation model indicates that the binder coverage is approximately 50% in the microscopy image in Fig. 1, whereas the binder coverage is only approximately 34% in a similar microscopy image of a Biax glass fibre fabric. This indicates that the assumption of homogeneous binder powder distribution is inadequate.

Another derived result using the U-Net segmentation model is the particle size distribution. Using the ensemble of microscopy images acquired the particle size distribution is calculated. The resulting binder powder particle size distribution for assumed circular particles is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Distribution of binder powder particle sizes extracted from segmented microscopy images using the U-Net model. Particle sizes are estimated assuming circular geometry.

Furthermore, the binder powder particle aspect ratios, defined as the ratio of the longest axis to the shortest axis of the segmented particles, are of interest. First, to check whether the assumption of circular particles used for the particle sizes was violated, but secondly, because the binder powder morphology is of interest and poorly studied. Figure 6 summarises the binder powder particle aspect ratios of the particles in the microscopy images segmented using the U-net segmentation model.

Figure 6: Distribution of aspect ratios (longest/shortest axis) of U-Net segmented binder particles, indicating general circularity.

The particle aspect ratios are as seen on Fig. 6, indicating that the particles are mostly approximately circular in shape, even though a smaller portion has slight ellipsoidal tendencies. It does, however, confirm that in general, it is not unreasonable to assume circular particles. These findings align well with microscopy image observations, e.g. see Fig. 1.

To give a more comprehensive understanding of the distribution of the binder powder on the glass fibre fabrics, one can investigate the binder coverage on smaller scales than the full microscopy images. This is because the region of influence for the particles is a lot smaller than the areas scanned, which makes it of interest to investigate whether there are areas with better or worse local coverage of the binder powder. The region of influence can be a moving window of a certain size, necessarily bigger than any individual powder particle. Using this moving window approach, a heatmap of local binder powder coverage percentages is constructed. Such a heatmap is overlaid on the example image (i.e. Fig. 1) in Fig. 7 below, where the moving window size is shown.

Figure 7: Heatmap of local binder powder coverage overlaid on the microscopy image from Fig. 1. The coverage is computed using a moving window approach to highlight spatial heterogeneity.

As seen in Fig. 7, the binder powder particles do not have a uniform coverage of the glass fibre fabric. Especially areas with stitching are lacking binder powder particles, resulting in near-zero coverage. Still, the deficient binder powder coverage is not limited to the stitching, as other areas are affected as well. Similarly, there are areas containing a lot of binder powders, which as a result yield the inhomogeneous distribution as indicated on the heatmap in Fig. 7.

To further quantify the local binder coverage of the considered fabrics, all of the microscopy images are considered to form a full distribution of local binder powder coverage percentages. That distribution is visualised in Fig. 8 below.

Figure 8: Distribution and boxplot of local binder powder coverage across all microscopy images.

The local binder powder particle coverage has a mean (and median) of approximately 47% but a standard deviation of approximately 17%-pts. The percentiles imply that 50% of the considered areas have a binder powder coverage between 32% and 57%, and that 95% of the considered areas have a binder powder coverage between 12% and 75%. This shows a wide range of local binder powder coverage, underlining the heterogeneous nature of the considered binder-powdered glass fibre fabrics.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Our findings using a U-Net deep CNN on partially annotated images suggest significantly improved segmentation of the microscopy images, resulting in accurate characterisation of the binder morphology and distribution. By comparing traditional and deep learning-based segmentation techniques, insights can be gained into the accuracy and reliability of each approach, paving the way for standardised, robust practices to characterise the binder powders applied to glass fibre fabrics. It has been shown how the distribution of local binder powder coverages has a large spread and can attain values from barely any binder powder to almost only binder powder. These insights contribute to a deeper understanding of the heterogeneity of the considered binder powder fabrics and the implications for composite processing and performance. The robust segmentation model developed highlights the potential for advanced automated image analysis tools for composite materials, which can pave the way for more data-driven approaches for material characterisation and better-informed processing.

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